

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 25

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 25

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 25:0 <i>A Psalm of David.</i></p>	<p>Psa. 25:1 לְדָוִד אֵלֶיךָ יְהוָה נַפְשִׁי אֲשָׂא: ²</p>
<p>Psa. 25:1 To You, O LORD, I ^alift up my soul.</p>	<p>אֵלֹהֵי בְנֵי בְטַחְתִּי אֶל־אֲבוֹשָׁה אֶל־יַעֲלֹצוּ</p>
<p>² O my God, in You ^aI trust, Do not let me ^bbe ashamed; Do not let my ^cenemies exult over me.</p>	<p>אֵיבֵי לִי: ³ גַּם כָּל־קִנְיֶיךָ לֹא יִבְשׂוּ יַבְשׁוּ</p>
<p>³ Indeed, ^anone of those who wait for You will be ashamed; ¹Those who ^bdeal treacherously without cause will be ashamed.</p>	<p>הַבּוֹגְדִים רִיקָם: ⁴ דְּרַכֶיךָ יְהוָה הוֹדִיעֵנִי</p>
<p>Psa. 25:4 ^aMake me know Your ways, O LORD; Teach me Your paths.</p>	<p>אֲרַחֲתֶיךָ לְמַדְנִי: ⁵ תִּדְרֹכְנִי בְּאֱמֻנָתְךָ </p>
<p>⁵ Lead me in ^aYour truth and teach me, For You are the ^bGod of my salvation; For You I ^cwait all the day.</p>	<p>וְלַמְדֵנִי כִּי־אֵתָהּ אֵלֹהֵי יִשְׂרָאֵל אוֹתְךָ קִוִּיתִי</p>
<p>⁶ ^aRemember, O LORD, Your compassion and Your lovingkindnesses, For they have been ^{1b}from of old.</p>	<p>כָּל־הַיּוֹם: ⁶ זְכוֹר־רַחֲמֶיךָ יְהוָה וַחֲסֵדֶיךָ כִּי</p>
<p>⁷ Do not remember the ^asins of my youth or my transgressions; ^bAccording to Your lovingkindness remember me, For Your ^c'goodness' sake, O LORD.</p>	<p>מַעֲוָלָם הַמָּחָה: ⁷ חַטָּאוֹת נַעֲוֵרַי וּפְשָׁעַי אֶל־</p>
<p>Psa. 25:8 ^aGood and ^bupright is the LORD; Therefore He ^cinstructs sinners in the way.</p>	<p>תִּזְכֹּר כַּחֲסֵדֶךָ זְכוֹר־לִי־אֵתָהּ לְמַעַן טוֹבֶיךָ</p>
<p>⁹ He ^aleads the ¹humble in justice, And He ^bteaches the ¹humble His way.</p>	<p>יְהוָה: ⁸ טוֹב־וַיִּשֶׁר יְהוָה עַל־בֶּן יוֹרֵה</p>
<p>¹⁰ All the paths of the LORD are ^alovingkindness and truth To ^bthose who keep His covenant and His testimonies.</p>	<p>חַטָּאִים בְּדַרְכֶּךָ: ⁹ יְדַרְכֶּךָ עֲנֻיִם בְּמִשְׁפַּט</p>
<p>¹¹ For ^aYour name's sake, O LORD, ^bPardon my iniquity, for it is great.</p>	<p>וַיְלַמֵּד עֲנֻיִם דַּרְכּוֹ: ¹⁰ כָּל־אֲרַחְוֹת יְהוָה</p>
	<p>חֶסֶד וָאֱמֻנָה לְנֹצְרֵי בְרִיתוֹ וְעַדְתָּיו: ¹¹ לְמַעַן־</p>
	<p>שִׁמְךָ יְהוָה וְסַלַּחְתָּ לְעֹוְנָי כִּי רַב־הוּא: ¹²</p>
	<p>מִי־זֶה הָאִישׁ יִרְאֵה יְהוָה יוֹרְנוּ בְּדַרְכֶּךָ יִבְחָר:</p>
	<p>¹³ נַפְשׁוֹ בְּטוֹב תִּלְוִין וְזָרְעוֹ יִירַשׁ אֲדָמָה: ¹⁴ סוֹד</p>
	<p>יְהוָה לִירְאָיו וּבְרִיתוֹ לְהוֹדִיעֵם: ¹⁵ עֵינַי</p>
	<p>תִּמְדוּ אֶל־יְהוָה כִּי הוּא־יוֹצֵא מִרְשַׁת רַגְלֵי:</p>
	<p>¹⁶ כִּפְנֵה־אֱלֹהֵי וַתִּגְנֵנִי כִּי־יָחִיד וְעֵנִי אָנִי: ¹⁷</p>
	<p>צָרוֹת לִבִּי תִרְחִיבוּ מִמְצוּקוֹתַי הוֹצֵאֵנִי: ¹⁸</p>
	<p>רָאה עֵינַי וְעַמְלִי וְשָׂא לְכָל־חַטָּאוֹתַי: ¹⁹</p>
	<p>רָאה־אוֹיְבֵי כִּי־רָבוּ וְשִׁנְאַת חַמָּס שִׁנְאוּנִי: ²⁰</p>
	<p>שִׁמְרַת נַפְשִׁי וַחֲצִילֵנִי אֶל־אֲבוֹשׁ כִּי־חֲסִיתִי</p>
	<p>בְּךָ: ²¹ תַּם־וַיִּשֶׁר יִצְרוּנִי כִּי קִוִּיתֶיךָ: ²² כִּי־תִרְחַק</p>
	<p>אֱלֹהִים אֶת־יִשְׂרָאֵל מִכָּל צָרוֹתָיו: --</p>

Psa. 25:12 Who is the man who ^afears the LORD?

He will ^binstruct him in the way he should choose.

¹³ His soul will ^aabide in ¹prosperity, And his ²descendants will ^binherit the ³land.

¹⁴ The ^{1a}secret of the LORD is for those who fear Him, ²And He will ^bmake them know His covenant.

¹⁵ My ^aeyes are continually toward the LORD, For He will ^{1b}pluck my feet out of the net.

Psa. 25:16 ^aTurn to me and be gracious to me, For I am ^blonely and afflicted.

¹⁷ ¹The ^atroubles of my heart are enlarged; Bring me ^bout of my distresses.

¹⁸ ^aLook upon my affliction and my ¹trouble, And ^bforgive all my sins.

¹⁹ Look upon my enemies, for they ^aare many, And they ^bhate me with violent hatred.

²⁰ ^aGuard my soul and deliver me; Do not let me ^bbe ashamed, for I take refuge in You.

²¹ Let ^aintegrity and uprightness preserve me, For ^bI wait for You.

²² ^aRedeem Israel, O God, Out of all his troubles.

References

<p>Psalm 25:1 ^aPs 86:4; 143:8</p> <p>Psalm 25:2 ^aPs 31:1 ^bPs 25:20; 31:1 ^cPs 13:4; 41:11</p> <p>Psalm 25:3 ¹Or <i>Let those...be ashamed</i> ^aPs 37:9; 40:1; Is 49:23 ^bPs 119:158; Is 21:2; Hab 1:13</p> <p>Psalm 25:4 ^aEx 33:13; Ps 27:11; 86:11</p> <p>Psalm 25:5 ^aPs 25:10; 43:3 ^bPs 79:9 ^cPs 40:1</p> <p>Psalm 25:6 ¹Or <i>everlasting</i> ^aPs 98:3 ^bPs 103:17</p> <p>Psalm 25:7 ^aJob 13:26; 20:11 ^bPs 51:1 ^cPs 31:19</p> <p>Psalm 25:8 ^aPs 86:5</p>	<p>Psalm 25:9 ¹Or <i>afflicted</i> ^aPs 23:3 ^bPs 27:11</p> <p>Psalm 25:10 ^aPs 40:11 ^bPs 103:18</p> <p>Psalm 25:11 ^aPs 31:3; 79:9 ^bEx 34:9</p> <p>Psalm 25:12 ^aPs 31:19 ^bPs 25:8; 37:23</p> <p>Psalm 25:13 ¹Lit <i>good</i> ²Lit <i>seed</i> ³Or <i>earth</i> ^aProv 1:33; Jer 23:6 ^bPs 37:11; 69:36; Matt 5:5</p> <p>Psalm 25:14 ¹Or <i>counsel or intimacy</i> ²Or <i>And His covenant, to make them know it</i> ^aProv 3:32; John 7:17 ^bGen 17:1, 2</p> <p>Psalm 25:15 ¹Lit <i>bring out</i></p>
--	--

^bPs 92:15

^cPs 32:8

Psalm 25:17

¹Some commentators read *Relieve the troubles of my heart*

^aPs 40:12

^bPs 107:6

Psalm 25:18

¹Lit *toil*

^a2 Sam 16:12; Ps 31:7

^bPs 103:3

Psalm 25:19

^aPs 3:1

^bPs 9:13

Psalm 25:20

^aPs 86:2

^bPs 25:2

Psalm 25:21

^aPs 41:12

^bPs 25:3

Psalm 25:22

^aPs 130:8

^aPs 123:2; 141:8

^bPs 31:4; 124:7

Psalm 25:16

^aPs 69:16

^bPs 143:4

Targum

Psa. 25:1 Of David. Before you, O LORD, I lift up my soul in prayer. ² O my God, in you I have put my trust; I will not be disappointed; my foes will not rejoice over me. ³ Truly, all who look to you will not be disappointed; robbers and rogues will be disappointed. ⁴ Show me your ways, O LORD; teach me your paths. ⁵ Lead me by your merit and teach me, for you are God, my redemption; in you I have placed my hope every day. ⁶ Remember your mercies, O LORD, and your favors, for they are eternal. ⁷ The sins of my youth and my transgressions do not remember; according to your goodness remember me, because of your grace, O LORD. ⁸ Good and upright is the LORD; therefore he teaches sinners on the path. ⁹ He guides the humble in judgment; and teaches the humble his way. ¹⁰ All the ways of the LORD are kindness and truth to those who keep his covenant and his testimony. ¹¹ Because of your Name, O LORD, you will forgive my sin, for it is great. ¹² Who is the man who is reverent in the presence of the LORD? He will teach him the way he has chosen. ¹³ His soul will lodge in kindness, and his children will inherit the earth. ¹⁴ The mystery of the LORD is revealed to those who fear him; and his covenant is to instruct them. ¹⁵ My eyes look always before the LORD, for he will bring my feet out of the trap. ¹⁶ Look towards me and have mercy on me, for I am alone and afflicted. ¹⁷ The troubles of my heart have spread; bring me out of my anguish. ¹⁸ See my pain and vexation, and forgive all my sins. ¹⁹ See my foes, for they have become many; and the enmity that the rapacious have towards me. ²⁰ Keep my soul and save me; I would not be disappointed because I hoped in you. ²¹ Innocence and honesty will guard me, for I hoped in your word. ²² Redeem Israel, O LORD, from all his troubles.

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses is in bold. The NASB gives a good picture of the spiritual awareness in the Psalm with the commentary offered. Therefore, a rewrite is not necessary.

Introduction

This Psalm describes King David's lifelong struggle to be on the "Path of the Upright." He begs for the LORD's assistance to help him stay on this path. The Sage Radak noted that this is the first Psalm arranged in the Alph-Beis, which means the first letters of the respective verses are in alphabetical order. However, the bet, vuv and kaf, letters are missing. It is unknown why David wrote the Psalm in this manner and why he left out the three missing letters.

Superscript

The NASB 1995 says, "A Psalm of David." The actual Hebrew says "of David."

Verse one

Lifting up the soul means bringing it closer to the LORD. In the Tree of Life, it would mean moving up a rung on the Ladder of Ascent. If a soul was in Malkhut, it would move to Yesod. From Yesod to Hod and so on. Moving up the ladder brings the soul closer to Keter and eventually to Ein Sof. David wished his soul to move closer to the LORD, which allowed the LORD to have a stronger hold on his direction. The Targum adds the words "in prayer." It is through prayer that the soul can move closer to the LORD.

Verse two

David placed all his trust and faith in the LORD, who ruled his destiny and guided his acts. He asked the LORD to help him to be satisfied with whatever happened in his life. By saying that he will not be ashamed by the results, he acknowledges that he will not be disappointed.

Verse three

No one who waits for divine assistance will be disappointed. The people who deal treacherously are those who have lost patience with waiting for the LORD. It is not a person's place to determine when and how the LORD will react to prayer or any assistance. Patience is required when waiting for the proper time that the LORD will assist. A breach of faith is always in vain because the person will become grievously disappointed. After all, what the person seeks will not be found.

Verse four

David wanted to know what the LORD had in store for him. He wanted to be shown the paths that his life would take. Was David showing patience by praying for the paths before the LORD was willing to share them with Him? A person can pray for the LORD to reveal His path for their life. Just remember that it is in the LORD's time that certain things may happen.

Verse five

The LORD can teach people how to behave appropriately. This includes a relationship with the LORD. David strived to be closer in his relationship with the LORD.

Verse six

David is asking the LORD to take care of him in the same way his mother attended to him when he was an infant. David became an adult, his mother's love for him would have changed from protector to supporter. The LORD was with David in his youth, even before David knew Him, and now that he was an adult, he still needed the love of the LORD to support him.

Verse seven

David asks the LORD to forget his childhood and youth mistakes. Children transgress the LORD's Law because they are not yet familiar with the Laws. David asks for the LORD's forgiveness for the transgressions of his youth.

Verse eight

The LORD deals kindly with humans and wants the best for us. However, at the same time, He expects us to live in a way that is worthy of His favor. The LORD does not abandon anyone who sins habitually. The LORD can strengthen a morally weak person. Such a person only needs to ask the LORD in prayer for the moral strength not to sin before Him.

Verse nine

The humble are persons whom the LORD has disciplined through judgment, the Sefirah Gevurah. Sinners, beware that the LORD seeks you out to change you and prepare your soul to return to the Lower Waters of Heaven.

Verse ten

This verse is in parallel with verse nine. Even the judgment of Gevurah does not mean that the love of the LORD from Chesed is not available to the person. The LORD created His covenant through Abraham and will always strive to make that happen.

Verse Eleven

The Name of the LORD (YHVH) offers a better future and renewed life for all who call upon the Name. The Name of the LORD is not spoken, but one can visualize it on paper or in mind. The Tzuruf prayer method is to see the Name of the LORD in front of you. Then see your prayers as beams of light passing through the Name. The prayers are acceptable to the LORD pass through the Name and are sanctified. The prayers that are not passed on are absorbed by the letters of the Name.

Verse twelve & thirteen

This is the result of a person who holds the LORD in reverence. The NASB uses the word "fear." Humans do not need to fear the LORD. Instead, they need to show reverence. This means that humans are to follow the ways and Laws that the LORD has given us, which are found in His Torah. When that is done, prosperity comes in this life to the person and his/her descendants. Having a good life means passing on a wonderful life to children. The children mainly model their parents' behavior. For the children that do this, their lives will be filled with prosperity.

Verse fourteen

This verse is a parallel verse because this idea has already been presented. The LORD will make known His presence to all who show reverence to Him by following the Torah. The covenant from the LORD is always in place. However, the people who respect the LORD will feel the results of the His presence and security.

Verse fifteen

David knew that the LORD was to deliver him from the tribulations of his life. The behavior that would have ensnared him into sin had been removed from his life path.

Verse sixteen

This verse is a parallel because this idea has already been presented. David tells the LORD that without His aid that David has no way to go. David needed the LORD to direct his life path, and he repeats the need for it.

Verse seventeen

This verse is a parallel because this idea has already been presented. David asks the LORD to bring him out of the troubles that have arisen in his life.

Verse eighteen

This verse is a parallel because this idea has already been presented. David knew that he had sinned greatly and grievously. Therefore, he prayed that the LORD will forgive him for these sins.

Verse nineteen

David believed that his sins caused Gevurah to bring up enemies who were to discipline him. Unfortunately, that discipline was David's death. That was not the punishment that he was looking for.

Verse twenty

The measure of David's sins was so great that he called upon the LORD to guard him against any future sins.

Verse twenty-one

David was looking for moral perfection and honest uprightness in his relations with his fellow persons. The later part of the verse is the statement that David knew that the LORD would help him.

Verse twenty-two

When David placed this Psalm into Israel's national collection of hymns, he added this final verse. David asked the LORD to forgive the nation for all its transgressions against the Torah.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

